

Interaction of Atoxyl with Mono Halogen Derivatives of the Substituted Amides of (a) Acetoacetic Acid and (b) Cyanacetic Acid : Synthesis of Organo-Arsenicals)

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Eighteen *p*-Arsonoanilino derivatives (Organo-arsenicals) have been synthesised from the interaction of atoxyl with mono halogen derivatives of the substituted amides of (a) acetoacetic acid and (b) cyanacetic acid respectively.

IN the present work, the study of the reactivity of the α -halogenated acetoacetylarnides and α -halogenated cyanacetylarnides with atoxyl is carried out. Attempts to study such reactivity have been made in the past^{1,2}.

In the present investigation, atoxyl(I) was allowed to react separately with the monochloro, monobromo or monoiodo derivatives of acetoacetylarnides (IIa) as well as with those of monobromo, or monoiodo cyanacetylarnides (IIb). In each case the halogen atom of the substituted amide reacted with the hydrogen atom of the amino group of atoxyl to give the corresponding α -(*p*-arsonoanilino)-acetoacetylarnides (IIIa) and α -(*p*-arsonoanilino)-cyanacetylarnides (IIIb).

Experimental

(a) α -(*p*-Arsonoanilino)-acetoacetylarnides : The compounds listed in Table 1 are prepared by the method described in an earlier communication³.

(b) α -(*p*-Arsonoanilino)-cyanacetylarnide : Monobromo or monoiodo derivatives of cyanacetylarnide (0.01M each) was separately dissolved in minimum quantity of water to which atoxyl (0.01M) dissolved in 5 ml. of water was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed and treated as above. The product in each case was crystallised from aqueous alcohol in tiny cluster. In the same way the compounds listed in table 2 have been prepared.

X = Cl, Br or I; a = COCH₃, R = phenyl, tolyl, xyllyl or naphthyl group; b = CN.

The bromo and iodo derivatives listed in table 3 are prepared by known methods^{4,5,6}. The

TABLE 1— α -(*p*-ARSONOANILINO)-ACETOACET ARYLAMIDES.

A = α -(*p*-Arsonoanilino)-acetoacet

Sr. No.	Compound	Molecular formula	M.P. °C	Yield %	Arsenic		Nitrogen	
					Found%	Reqd. %	Found%	Reqd. %
1.	A-Anilide	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ O ₅ N ₂ As	240	28.13	19.33	19.12	—	—
2.	A- <i>p</i> -chloroanilide	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₅ N ₂ ClAs	212	33.62	17.34	17.99	—	—
3.	A- <i>o</i> -toluidide	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ O ₅ N ₂ As	226	29.63	18.98	18.45	7.21	6.90
4.	A- <i>p</i> -toluidide	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ O ₅ N ₂ As	230	32.09	18.87	18.45	6.96	6.90
5.	A-1 : 2 : 4-xylidide	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ O ₅ N ₂ As	218	29.84	17.19	17.84	—	—
6.	A-1 : 3 : 4-xylidide	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ O ₅ N ₂ As	226	23.86	17.25	17.84	6.60	6.67
7.	A- <i>p</i> -phenitidide	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ O ₅ N ₂ As	198	27.58	16.93	17.19	—	—
8.	A- α -Naphthylamide	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₅ N ₂ As	252	29.41	17.47	16.91	5.93	6.32
9.	A- β -naphthylamide	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₅ N ₂ As	268	27.15	16.32	16.91	—	—

All mps. are uncorrected.

TABLE 2— α -(*p*-ARSONOANILINO)-CYANACET ARYLAMIDESB = α -(*p*-Arsonoanilino)-cyanacet-

Sr. No.	Compound	Molecular formula	M.P. °C	Yield %	Arsenic		Nitrogen	
					Found%	Reqd. %	Found%	Reqd. %
1.	B-anilide	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₃ As	225	29.34	19.58	20.00	—	—
2.	B- <i>o</i> -toluidide	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₃ As	212	23.14	19.50	19.29	—	—
3.	B- <i>m</i> -toluidide	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₃ As	197	25.71	29.02	19.29	—	—
4.	B- <i>p</i> -toluidide	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₃ As	225	28.28	18.66	19.29	10.90	10.80
5.	B-benzylamide	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₃ As	208	29.56	19.94	19.29	—	—
6.	B- <i>o</i> -anisidide	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₅ N ₃ As	232	34.10	19.21	18.52	—	—
7.	B- <i>o</i> -phenitidide	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₅ N ₃ As	259	28.64	17.41	17.90	—	—
8.	B-1 : 3 : 4-xylydide	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₃ As	262	32.25	18.38	18.61	10.33	10.42
9.	B- α -naphthylamide	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₃ As	282	32.94	17.42	17.65	—	—

All m.ps. are uncorrected.

TABLE 3—MONOHALO ACETOACET ARYLAMIDES

(M = Monobromo acetoacet-)

(K = Monochloro acetoacet-)

Sr. No.	Compound	Molecular formula	M.P. °C	Yield %	Halogen		Nitrogen	
					Found%	Reqd. %	Found%	Reqd. %
1.	M- <i>p</i> -toluidide	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₂ NBr	149	65.8	29.79	29.67	—	—
2.	M- <i>o</i> -toluidide	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₂ NBr	90	50.0	30.04	29.67	—	—
3.	M- <i>p</i> -chloroanilide	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₂ NClBr	145	61.5	—	—	5.20	4.82
4.	M- <i>p</i> -phenitidide	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ NBr	149	75.0	26.81	26.86	—	—
5.	M-1 : 2 : 4-xylydide	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ NBr	128	66.0	28.06	28.16	—	—
6.	M-1 : 3 : 4-xylydide	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ NBr	126	70.0	28.11	28.16	—	—
7.	K- <i>p</i> -toluidide	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₂ NCl	86	57.8	15.36	15.74	—	—
8.	K- α -Naphthylamide	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₂ NCl	135	66.0	13.11	13.58	—	—
9.	K- β -naphthylamide	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₂ NCl	93	70.5	13.10	13.58	—	—

All m.ps. are uncorrected.

chloro derivatives are prepared by the method given below :

Monochloro acetoacet p-toluidide : Acetoacet *p*-toluidide (0.01M) dissolved in 10–15 ml. of glacial acetic acid in presence of a trace of Iodine crystal as catalyst, to which sulphuryl chloride (0.01M) in cold was added. The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 3 hr. and on pouring in cold water, it gave a white product, which was crystallised from alcohol. This method gave better yield and cleaner product than that with dry ether⁷.

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